

Analyzing Impact of Freelancing Business during COVID-19 during Second Wave: A Case Study of Sindh-Pakistan

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Abstract:

This research investigates Analyzing impact of Freelancing business during COVID-19 during second wave : A case study of Sindh-Pakistan. Data were collected from primary sources sample of 100 freelancing business owners were collected from Sukkur, Shikarpur, Larkana, Hyderabad and Karachi. Data were analyzed by using smart PLS. According to results revealed that during COVID-19 has much impact on freelancing business in the include research music, writing ,acting ,computer programming, web design , graphic design, translating and illustrating films and video production and other forms of piece work which have some cultural theories considered as central to the cognitive - cultural economy. It was further revealed that hiring freelancers company can also save building and office expenses while freelancers do their work at home or pay rent for their own offices same time they purchase seats to maintain office environment for meeting their tasks perfectly.

Keywords: Freelancing Business, COVID-19 Second Wave

Introduction:

Freelancer or freelance worker are terms commonly used for a person who is self-employed. Freelancer are sometime represented by a company or a temporary agency that resells freelance labor to clients other work. Independently or use professional association or website to get work. The term Freelance is most common in culture and creative industries and use of this term may indicate participation therein fields,professions and industries where freelancing is predominant include music,writing ,acting ,computer programming, web design , graphic design, translating and illustrating films and vedio production and other forms of piece work which have some cultural theories considered as central to the cognitive - cultural economy

History

The word freelance first time use in 1800 by sir "walter scott's" he introduce his first army they would fight for whichever country who paid the most .

Before freelance word It knew as stipendiarii (latin word :soilders) as now a days people working as freelacer and term is Freelance

The hired army were common after 1000 A.D for war and security purpose. The hired soilders were refered as condottieres .this was a mojour piece of military compagins rea of 12th to 14th centuries condotierres which refers to leaders of mercenary soilders and lansquent term was used for soilders. The lansquent term which refers to german hired soilders were known as stipendiarii.

Types of freelancing or freelancing job

To start a work quickly at home freelancing is best option

People who want to earn side cash whatever the reason there is no denying that freelancing jobs are on the rise

Now here are 7 most common types of freelance jobs

- 1- Freelance writer
- 2- virtual assistant
- 3- Freelance web developer or programmer

- 4- Graphic Designer
- 5- Book keeping
- 6- Freelance photography
- 7- search engine optimization

WHEN IT BECAME POPULAR IN PAKISTAN

2017 was the year when freelancer become popular in Pakistan and online labour index published in 2017 Pakistan is among the top five countries in the world when it comes to freelancing and generate significant amount of 0.5 billion from freelancing

Pakistan has got the fourth position globally in category of software development and technology.

WHY FREELANCING \WHY COMPANIES HIRE FREELANCER

- 1 To promote your idea and invention on global scale
- 2 Freelancing is fast going trend almost all type of business in every industry are embracing freelance talents
- 3 Freelancing can be cut off company expenses to pay sick pay and holidays pay.
- 4 when companies hire full-time employee they have to pay benefits like health insurance ,bonus incentives etc
- 5 freelancer are making bridge 1st world and 3rd world countries
- 6 Freelancers are free agent it is another name of on-demand workers
- 7 By hiring freelancers company can also save building and office expenses while freelancers do their work at home or pay rent for their own offices same time they purchase seats to maintain office environment for meeting their tasks perfectly .

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

TO INVESTIGATE INCREASING CONDITION OF FREELANCING IN PAKISTAN IN REFERENCE OF EPIDEMIC CONDITION

TO INVESTIGATE IMPACT OF HIRING FREELANCERS ON REQUIRMENT OF REGULAR EMPLOYEE